

THE COMPRESSION BUCKLING BEHAVIOUR OF HIGHLY CURVED PANELS
OF CARBON FIBRE REINFORCED PLASTIC

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Summary

The initial buckling and post-buckling performance in compression of nine unstiffened curved panels is described. The panels, of length 540 mm, 250 mm radius, 2 mm thickness and 420 mm arc length have clamped ends and simply supported edges using conventional support arrangements. Six of the panels have different lay-ups and three have geometric imperfections in the form of lateral bulges of different magnitudes for comparison with an equivalent perfect panel. Testing was carried out under displacement control to avoid panel failure at buckling which occurred violently with a drop of almost 50% in load. No significant damage was detected at buckling and large increases in end shortening were required to cause failure which took place at a lower load than initial buckling in every case. Imperfections up to $\frac{1}{2}$ panel thickness had very little effect on buckling load. A range of theoretical methods including nonlinear finite element, finite strip and Rayleigh Ritz were assessed. The FE predictions tend to overestimate the buckling load by up to 20% but, considering the complex behaviour at buckling and the limitations of the element used, the agreement is encouraging. The other methods gave quick results of similar accuracy.

Introduction

An understanding of the behaviour of thin curved composite panels under destabilising forces is an essential requirement in aircraft design. The increasing usage of Carbon Fibre Reinforced Plastic (CFRP) in the curved surfaces of highly loaded rear fuselage areas has highlighted the need for research in the buckling and strength of such panels. Destabilising forces are compression and shear combined with lateral (pressure) loading and the effect of geometric imperfections which is believed to limit the buckling load¹.

Cylinders and curved panels are known to exhibit unstable behaviour at the initial buckling point; a sudden mode change takes place with a drop in load carrying capacity at constant end displacement. This is in contrast to the response of flat plates which exhibit stable buckling behaviour with no loss of load. Fig 1 illustrates qualitatively some characteristic buckling curves for panels at increasing curvature and shows the difference in general behaviour between flat and curved panels. With increasing curvature the theoretical initial buckling point (the bifurcation point) is increased considerably beyond the flat plate value. However, it is expected that the sensitivity to imperfection will also increase with curvature so that the experimental buckling load (the limit point) may fall significantly short of the bifurcation point for practical panels with imperfection. It is important therefore to understand the effects of imperfection and to include them in theoretical methods. The explosive buckling behaviour of highly curved panels raises the question of whether the post-buckled strength of CFRP, with its inherent weakness in interlaminar shear and brittle failure characteristics, is sufficient to allow the initial buckling load to be exceeded or even survived.

Historically there have always been wide differences between predicted and measured buckling loads for curved panels, largely because simplified linear analyses were used inappropriately to find the buckling loads for structures containing imperfections. However with the introduction of powerful nonlinear computer methods the possibility exists of extending the analysis into the post-buckled range and to predict the nonlinear path and limit point for imperfect panels.

Much interest is currently being shown in buckling behaviour and recently published investigations include the work of Khot and Bauld² who tested curved panels with clamped ends and either supported or unsupported edges. Buckling loads were compared with finite difference predictions (CLAPP) including imperfections and reasonable agreement was reported. Becker, Palazotto and Khot³ report work on thin (1 mm) panels of 300 mm radius with minimal imperfections and compare test results with finite difference predictions (STAGS-C) for linear bifurcation and nonlinear collapse. The collapse analysis yielded results in good agreement with experiment but the predicted initial buckling loads were up to 45% higher than test results. In the present work a range of new theoretical methods will be assessed against test results for both initial buckling and post-buckling behaviour. The methods to be considered are the finite element version of STAGS⁴, the finite strip based program VIPASA⁵, and the Rayleigh-Ritz programme BUCCAL⁶ developed at Imperial College, the latter two being assessed for their value in quick analysis.

This paper discusses the initial buckling and post-buckling behaviour of nine curved panels of radius 250 mm, thickness 2 mm, and compares the test results with theoretical predictions. Six of the panels, varying in lay-up but nominally perfect (minimal imperfections), are considered for the

effect of lay-up changes on performance. The other three have the same lay-up but contain geometric imperfection in the form of lateral bulges of different magnitudes; their performance is compared with that of an equivalent perfect panel.

Table I. Curved Panels - Lay-up and Dimensions

Series A: radius $R = 250$ mm, thickness $t = 2$ mm
 circumference $b = 444$ mm (420 mm between supports)
 length $L = 540$ mm

No	Lay-up	Description
A1	$(+, -, -, +, 0, 0, 0, 0)_S$	blocked lay-up, $50\% 0^\circ$, $50\% \pm 45^\circ$
A2	$(+, -, +, -, +, -, +, -)_S$	distributed, $100\% \pm 45^\circ$
A3	$(+, 0, -, 0, +, 0, -, 0)_S$	distributed, $50\% 0^\circ$, $50\% \pm 45^\circ$
A4	$(+, 0, 0, 0, 0, -, 0, 0)_S$	$75\% 0^\circ$, $25\% \pm 45^\circ$
A5	$(+, 90, 0, 0, 0, -, 0, 0)_S$	$62.5\% 0^\circ$, $25\% \pm 45^\circ$, $12.5\% 90^\circ$
A6	$(+, -, +, 0, -, +, 0, -)_S$	$25\% 0^\circ$, $75\% \pm 45^\circ$
A7	as A3	$\frac{1}{2}$ mm imperfection (outward)
A8	as A3	$\frac{1}{2}$ mm imperfection (inward)
A9	as A3	0.9 mm imperfection (outward)

Layer stiffness properties

$$E_{11} = 130 \text{ GN/m}^2, E_{22} = 10 \text{ GN/m}^2, G_{12} = 6 \text{ GN/m}^2, \nu_{12} = 0.3$$

Fig 1 Effect of curvature on panel buckling

Fig 2 Photograph of curved panel compression specimen

Test Specimens and Testing

Configuration and Materials

The test panels considered in this paper are all of radius 250 mm, with length, arc and thickness of 540 mm, 444 mm (420 mm between supports) and 2 mm respectively. Table I gives details of the range of panel specimens chosen. Three of the panels were manufactured with a geometric imperfection formed by interposing a graduated stack of peel-ply layers between the cylindrical mould surface and the laminate stack. The resulting lateral bulge is in the form of a pyramidal hill extending over the whole panel. Panels A7, A8 and A9 contain imperfections of nominally $+\frac{1}{2}$ mm (outwards), $-\frac{1}{2}$ mm (inwards) and + 1 mm (outwards) respectively. The imperfections were measured and used in the theoretical calculations. All the panels are composed of 16 layers of pre-preg (XAS-914C) in combinations of 0° , $+45^\circ$ and 90° appropriate to the expected aircraft loading in bending and torsion. The proportions vary widely from $100\% \pm 45^\circ$ to $75\% 0^\circ$, $25\% \pm 45^\circ$ including distributed and blocked forms in order to investigate the potential trade-off between initial buckling stress and post-buckling strength.

Test Specimen

A photograph of the test specimen showing the main features is given as Fig 2. In principle the specimen is similar to the type often used in flat plate buckling experiments. It has curved aluminium alloy (L65) end blocks with a curved slot 25 mm deep to accept the panel. The slot is end-milled 6 mm wide for ease of machining and packed at assembly with a 4 mm curved strip to give the correct adhesive thickness, resulting in encastred support conditions along the curved edges. Conventional steel knife-edge members bolted to steel channels are used to give the simple support condition along the straight edges. To ensure alignment and uniform load distribution the assembly is bonded under load between the plattens of the testing machine.

Instrumentation and Testing

The information required from the tests is the load, deflection and strain histories in all modes of deformation up to failure. Overall load-displacement curves, corrected for test machine flexibility, were obtained from an XY plotter connected to the test machine load cell and displacement transducers. Standard metal foil strain gauges positioned on both sides of the panel at the nine internal quarter points were used to measure strain. The geometric imperfections and buckled mode were measured by a displacement transducer mounted on the saddle of a motorised height gauge clamped to the test machine. Combined with a sensitive XY plotter this arrangement enabled small pre-buckled wave forms to be recorded in addition to imperfections and post-buckled shapes. The lateral deflection at an expected buckle peak was also measured by deflection transducer and recorded continuously with load. Finally the post-buckled modes were photographed during test for observation of modal development and comparison with theoretical predictions. The tests were carried out in a Schenck servo-hydraulic test machine of 400 kN capacity under displacement control.

Observations on Buckling Behaviour

In this section the overall response of the panels loaded up to initial buckling and through to failure is described. The tests were carried out by the application of controlled end displacement rather than

load. In this way the load changes through buckling can be observed even when buckling results in a loss of load carrying capacity. The discussion naturally divides between the nominally perfect panels, where lay-up differences influence behaviour, and the effect of geometric imperfection on panels of a given lay-up.

Tests on Nominally Perfect Panels

Six panels were tested, given as A1 to A6 on Table I. The behaviour of these panels was broadly similar so attention will be focused on one example, panel A1, and a full description given while the behaviour of the other five will be described in less detail.

Fig 3 Load-displacement curve — panel A1

Characteristic Buckling Behaviour. The curve of load against displacement (end shortening) gives a good description of overall behaviour and this is shown for panel A1 as Fig 3. This curve combines the results of two tests, the first up to initial buckling and back to zero load, and the second through buckling to failure. The full lines are the response on the stable branches of the curve whereas the broken lines are the "jumps" in load from one stable branch to another, under controlled displacement. At buckling, a large drop in load (43%) takes place, caused by the change in stiffness from predominantly membrane action (unbuckled) to combined membrane and bending action (buckled). If the displacement is then reduced the second equilibrium branch descends and then increases until the vertical tangent point is reached when another, smaller, jump in load occurs as the panel unbuckles. The two minor peaks in the curve

at this point are caused by the sequential unbuckling action of the two buckles. With further reduction in displacement the first stable equilibrium path is then retraced to the origin. The first post-buckled shape is shown in the photograph in Fig 4 as two symmetrical inward buckles about 10 mm deep.

Considering the complete response curve in Fig 3 four distinct phases are evident:-

- 1 1st SEP: linear pre-buckling.
- 2 2nd SEP: post-buckled mode with two symmetric inward buckles.
- 3 3rd SEP: post-buckled mode with an additional inward buckle in the lower quarter of the panel centre.
- 4 Failure: final inward buckle in the upper quarter of the panel centre.

The sequence of development of the third and fourth buckles may be explained by consideration of the buckled shape. If it is assumed that these two buckles are unlikely to occur simultaneously then the third will stiffen the unbuckled part of the panel by increasing its local curvature in the reverse sense to the shape of the fourth buckle. The fourth buckle can then only take place with a further increase in load. The post-buckle curve shows continuous unstiffening accentuated through the second mode change. After edge-failure the central region of the panel remained unbuckled and carried 23% of the maximum load in an intensely buckled form. However, the failure occurred at 105 kN, only 78% of maximum load, implying that this panel would have no post-buckled performance in a load-controlled situation.

Fig 4 Photograph of 1st post buckled shape, Panel A1

Fig 5 Photograph of final post buckled shape, Panel A1

The final post-buckled shape of the failed panel is shown in Fig 5 and deflection scans for the two significant positions of quarter arc and centre line generators are given in Fig 6. The top curve is the shape of the panel at the quarter position immediately after initial buckling with mode 2 only present (ie SEP 2); however this shape did not change much with load increase. The panel centre is relatively undeformed at this stage but after initial failure at the edges it became highly buckled as shown by the lower curve. Significant features on the curves are the large depth of the buckles and the high curvature near the peaks of the inward buckles. The inward direction of the initial buckle formation may have significance for the effect of imperfections; it is likely that inward imperfections will be more detrimental than outward imperfections. This possibility is to be studied in further tests.

The strains at the quarter arc and centre line positions are shown in Figs 7 and 8 respectively. The behaviour shown in Fig 7 is linear up to buckling which occurs with a profound change to flexural behaviour. The flexural strains then increase up to failure at a maximum recorded axial surface strain of $+7200 \mu\epsilon$. The maximum circumferential strain at this position (the buckle peak) was measured by triaxial gauge as $+4500 \mu\epsilon$ which is Poisson's ratio (0.65) x longitudinal strain showing that no lateral constraint forces were present. Fig 8 gives the strains on the vertical centre line and shows the severe effect of the third buckle at the second mode change. The maximum recorded surface strain is about $+8000 \mu\epsilon$ (flexural) at the third buckle peak. Both strain plots show increasing nonlinearity at some of the gauge positions just before buckling, behaviour which is not evident from the load-displacement curve. The overall load/axial strain response is derived from Fig 3 by calculating average strain from axial displacement. The values derived are applicable to non-buckling areas and can therefore be taken as the membrane strain at the knife edge supports which is given as $-5500 \mu\epsilon$ at failure.

Fig 6 Deflection scans of buckling mode, Panel A1

Fig 7 Strain behaviour, 1/4 arc generator, Panel A1

Fig 8 Strain behaviour, panel centre generator, Panel A1

Turning now to the mechanism of failure: some evidence of the failure mode and extent can be seen in Fig 5 showing surface delamination of the $+45^\circ$ layers. The extent of the damage was identified by radiographic investigation and is limited to the areas shown in Fig 9. The nature of the internal damage, shown on the X-ray photographs in Fig 10 is fracture of the main load carrying layers (the 0° layers) and extensive delamination of both the 0° and $+45^\circ$ layers. There is also evidence of surface cutting of the inner surface layers by the knife edge supports but this is thought to be post-failure damage. The complex nature of the fracture makes it difficult to determine with certainty the cause of failure but it is likely that the delamination promoted failure of the main load carrying layers (the 0° material) by buckling of the individual layers. Considering the width/thickness ratios resulting from the multiple delamination observed at the panel edge it is certainly feasible that layer buckling failure could take place at the membrane strain of $5500 \mu\epsilon$ measured for this position. Furthermore it is likely that the extremely blocked nature of the lay-up contributed to delamination. However, the blocked lay-up may also have been the reason for the limited propagation of damage.

Effect of Lay-up on Buckling Behaviour. The six panels A1 to A6 varied widely in lay-up configuration from all $+45^\circ$ (A2) to predominantly 0° (A4) and included fully blocked and fully distributed lamination (A1 and A3). In addition the effect of 90° layers was studied with panel A5. The wide differences in membrane and flexural stiffness were expected to influence the buckling behaviour and this aspect is discussed below.

The load-displacement curves for all six panels are shown on Fig 11 and the initial buckling loads are summarised in the table below.

Panel	A1	A2	A3	A4	A5	A6
Lay-up	50/50/0 blocked	0/100/0	50/50/0 distributed	75/25/0	62.5/25/12.5	25/75/0
Buckling load kN	134	79	134	117	131	130

Considering first the buckling loads achieved, but ignoring A2 for the present, four of the panels (A1, A3, A5 and A6) were very close despite the differences in lay-up. This can be contrasted with flat plate behaviour where initial buckling is proportional to flexural stiffness through the term, $f(D) = (D_{11}D_{22})^{1/2} + D_{12} + 2D_{33}$, giving differences of up to 27% for the A1 and A5 lay-ups. The variation of layer distribution, either blocked or fully distributed (A1 and A3), had no effect whereas in flat plates a difference of 20% is expected. Although the variation of buckling load with flexural stiffness was not strong it had some effect since panel A4 with lowest $f(D)$ also had the lowest buckling load of the panels in this group. Turning now to panel A2, this panel behaved anomalously with the lowest buckling load of all despite having the greatest value of $f(D)$. However, the measured buckling strain of about $7400 \mu\epsilon$ was much higher than for any other panel. Material nonlinearity can explain the low load value (see Fig 11).

The load-displacement curves in Fig 11 show that the behaviour of all the panels was similar. The greatest load achieved was at initial buckling

Fig 9 Areas of failure, Panel A1

a

b

Fig 10a&b X-ray photographs of Panel A1 failure

Fig 11 Load-displacement curves for panels A1 to A6

A1

A2

A3

A4

A5

A6

A6

Fig 12 Photographs of final post-buckled shapes, A1 to A6

with failure taking place at increased displacement but reduced load. In some cases post-buckled mode changes took place with the formation of more buckles and a further reduction in post-buckled stiffness at each mode change. Photographs of the panels just before failure show the fully developed post-buckled modes in Fig 12. All the panels had different post-buckle modes as shown. However, the same panel tested twice would sometimes exhibit different post-buckled modes each time at virtually the same buckling load; this occurred with panel A3 which behaved on one occasion as panel A1. It was noticeable that changes in mode affected the violence of buckling and the resulting drop in load; panels which adopted a four buckle mode such as A3 and A4 behaved less violently than panels which initially adopted a two buckle mode such as A1 and A5. Panel A2 behaved differently from the others in its amplitude of pre-buckled shape; at the high buckling strain of about $7000 \mu\epsilon$ a short wavelength buckled shape shown in Fig 13 was recorded. This changed to the two buckle form shown in Fig 12, also containing components of the pre-buckle form near to the end blocks.

Failure initiated from the edges by, it is thought, growth of delamination and fracture of the main load carrying layers. However, the detailed mechanisms of failure have not been studied because none of the panels had post-buckled strength above the initial buckling load. Consequently the emphasis was on understanding the parameters influencing initial buckling behaviour.

Fig 13 Modal development of Panel A2

The Influence of Geometric Imperfection on Buckling Load

In much published work in the past (see for example reviews in References 1 and 8) deviations from assumed "perfect" shape have been taken as the main reason for reductions in buckling load compared with the theoretical predictions. In the present work this possibility is assessed with four panels with the same lay-up and planform, three of which contain geometric imperfection to be compared with a nominally perfect panel. The imperfections, of known form, were measured by scanning with a displacement transducer along a generator at the panel centre. This was carried out during test and repeated at load increments to measure the subsequent lateral deflections and deformation modes both pre and post buckling. The panels considered in this group are A3, the nominally perfect panel, and A7, A8 and A9 which contained lateral bulges of $+1/2$ mm (outward), $-1/2$ mm (inward) and $+0.9$ mm (outward) respectively.

Buckling Load and Mode

The load-displacement curves are shown in Fig 14 and the loads achieved are given in the table below.

Panel No	Imperfection magnitude, mm	Buckling load, kN
A3	0	134
A7	+0.5	132
A8	-0.5	135
A9	+0.9	129

Fig 14 Load-displacement curves for Panels A3 and A7 to A9

As can be seen there is very little difference in the initial buckling loads for panels A3, A7 and A8 despite the imperfections. Indeed the most imperfect panel (A9) buckled at only 3.7% less load than A3, the nominally perfect panel. It appears that imperfections of at least this magnitude (about half panel thickness) are necessary before the buckling load is affected. In fact the only significant effect was to modify the post-buckled response. Photographs of the final post-buckled mode in Fig 15 show A3 with a skewed mode of 6 buckles whereas A7, A8 and A9 displayed the doubly symmetric four buckle mode. Curves of load against deflection in Fig 16 show the response measured at the centre line quarter point position. The pre-buckling behaviour, similar for all four panels, shows the outwards deflection, increasing in rate for panels A3, A7 and A8 just before buckling. The three imperfect panels show much more dramatic buckling with greater deflection and load-drop than the perfect panel.

Development of Pre and Post-buckled Modes

It is well known in the buckling of cylinders that the mode shape just prior to buckling, comprising short wavelength buckles, changes dynamically at the buckling point to a simpler shape with fewer, deeper buckles. This behaviour was also observed in the present tests and the modal development for the four panels is shown in Fig 17. The pre buckle shape of the plain panel (A3) consists of barrelling (outwards) displacement superposed with a number of small amplitude waves, difficult to detect, those at the ends being most pronounced. This behaviour was similar for all the nominally perfect panels. The shape of the lateral bulge at the indicated generator position for the three imperfect panels is shown by the zero load trace and the other traces show the pre-buckled deformation with superposed wavelets, and the large amplitude buckled form.

Theoretical Analysis

This section will describe the various theoretical analysis techniques used to predict the initial and post-buckling behaviour of the range of test panels. Investigations using the STAGSC-1 FE programme are treated in some detail and the results for buckling load of the Rayleigh-Ritz program BUCCAL and the finite strip program VIPASA are briefly described and presented in tabular form for comparison. Two main areas of discussion are presented; firstly the analysis of nominally perfect panels differing only in lay-up and secondly the treatment of geometric imperfections for panels of the same lay-up and external dimensions.

For each panel tested both a linear bifurcation buckling analysis and a nonlinear static analysis were performed using the STAGSC-1 code. The mesh size of the model was established by a convergence analysis on one panel required to give less than 1% difference in bifurcation buckling load; this established a mesh of 20 x 20 elements over the full panel. The element used, designated as 411, is a general rectangular plate element (flat) of the Clough-Felippa type with displacement incompatibility removed at non-planar edge connections. This element has seven degrees-of-freedom at each corner node (3 translations, 3 rotations and a normal rotation between intersecting grid lines) plus a midside degree of freedom in the tangential displacing direction. The boundary conditions applied to the model match those given by the experimental set-up, ie encastré curved edges and simply supported straight edges with tangential sliding movement and "drilling" freedoms allowed. As in the tests load is applied in the form of a uniform increase in end displacement (end shortening). It should be noted that the 12 mm overhangs outside the knife-edge supports were not modelled explicitly. However, loads derived from all the analysis methods were corrected to include the extra material.

A3 - 50/50/0 stratified

A7 - $\frac{1}{2}$ mm outward imperfections

A8 - $\frac{1}{2}$ mm inward imperfections

A9

Fig 15 Photographs of final post-buckled modes, A3 and A7 to A9

Fig 16 Load-deflection curves for Panels A3 and A7 to A9

The linear bifurcation buckling analysis indicated that all the panels analysed had a tendency to "barrel" outwards before initial buckling, similar to the test experience. This barrelling effect is illustrated by a contour plot in Fig 18 showing the deformed shape of panel A1 before initial buckling. The small out-of-plane displacement which occurs usually proved to be sufficient to ensure convergence of the nonlinear static analysis in contrast to the case of flat panels where it is necessary to impose small initial imperfections. The solution strategy adopted for the nonlinear analysis was the incremental/iterative method (path length algorithm) developed by Riks⁹. Such a strategy has made it possible to continue the majority of analyses through the limit point.

Analysis of Nominally Perfect Panels

Panels A1 to A6 detailed in Table 1 were analysed as outlined above. The flexural and membrane stiffness terms were derived using laminated plate theory based on the unidirectional stiffness properties given in Table I. A comparison of the predicted buckling loads given by STAGSC-1, VIPASA and BUCCAL with the measured results for all panels tested is given in Table II. It is evident that the predictions are much more lay-up dependent than the test results. Considering the STAGSC-1 bifurcation analyses first the predicted buckling loads range from 123 kN for panel A2 to 173 kN for panel A3. It is interesting to note that the two panels (A2 & A4) with the lowest predicted initial buckling loads both represented extremes in flexural or membrane stiffness, A2 having the lowest membrane stiffness and highest flexural (twisting) stiffness whereas the reverse is true for A4. The maximum initial buckling load occurs for panels with relatively high stiffness in both membrane and flexure such as A3 with the 50/50/0 lay-up.

The predicted initial buckling mode shapes vary from panel to panel as shown on Fig 19. The most common shape, predicted for panels A1, A2 and A6, has five buckles along the length. Panels A4 and A5, identical but for the presence of 90° layers in panel A5, have the same shape, ie three buckles running diagonally across the panel. However, the calculated load at which this initial buckling mode shape occurs for each panel differs by 14%. Finally the initial buckling mode shape predicted for panel A3, with the highest predicted load, has the form of one dominant buckle near each straight edge.

The nonlinear static analysis of panels A1 to A6 results in the load-displacement curves shown on Fig 20. These illustrate how similarly the panels behave in the immediate post-buckled region. The dynamic snap-through at buckling is clearly evident as it was on test. Although it is of interest to extend the load displacement curves further into the post-buckled region it is the initial buckling load which is important since none of the panels showed any post-buckled strength on test. The buckling loads predicted by the nonlinear analyses do not always fall below those given by the bifurcation analyses as expected. However, the high bifurcation buckling load predicted for panel A3 was reduced by 6% using the nonlinear method.

The initial buckling mode shape predicted by the nonlinear analysis of each panel agrees with that predicted by the bifurcation buckling analysis. However, the post-buckled mode shapes predicted for each panel by the nonlinear analysis agree well with test; these post-buckled shapes are simpler with fewer, deeper buckles appearing than the initial buckling mode. Ignoring panel A1 for the present, the nonlinear analysis of panels A2 and A6 are very similar; both predicted a post-buckled mode shape of two inward buckles diagonally opposite each other as shown on Fig 21. The post-buckled mode

Fig 17 Modal development of Panels A3 and A7 to A9

TABLE II. Comparison of Predicted and Measured Buckling Loads
(kN) for Panels A1 to A9

Panel Ident	STAGSC-1		VIPASA	BUCCAL	Experimental Results
	Bifurcation	Nonlinear			
A1	149.2	151.5	141.0	169.1	134
A2	123.5	126.1	137.4	106.7	79
A3	173.2	162.9	130.2	149.0	134
A4	124.9	-	105.2	125.8	117
A5	142.8	141.8	116.8	148.0	131
A6	155.8	155.8	151.2	150.1	130
A7	175.3	169.1	-	-	132
A8	170.5	157.8	-	-	135
A9	176.4	-	-	-	129

TABLE III. Comparison of STAGSC-1 Prediction for Uniform and
Non-uniform Loading

Panel Ident	Non-uniform Loading, kN			Uniform Loading, kN
	L Edge	R Edge	Mean	
A1	140.9	154.9	147.9	149.2
A2	116.5	128.1	122.3	123.5
A3	159.3	175.2	167.2	173.2
A4	116.1	127.7	121.9	124.9
A5	133.4	146.7	140.0	142.8
A6	146.5	161.2	153.8	155.8
A7	161.5	177.7	169.6	175.3
A8	156.7	172.3	164.5	170.5
A9	162.4	178.6	170.5	176.4

Fig 18 Predicted pre-buckling deflection of Panel A1

Fig 19 Initial buckling mode shapes predicted by bifurcation buckling analyses of the nominally perfect panels

Fig 20 Load-displacement, nominally perfect panels

Panel A2 (similar for Panel A6)

*Maximum out-of-plane displacement = 2.7908 mm
Load = 93.41 kN, end shortening = 3.03857 mm

Panel A3 (similar for Panel A5)

*Maximum out-of-plane displacement = 1.4097 mm
Load = 130.24 kN, end shortening = 1.11139 mm

Fig 21 Post-buckled mode shapes predicted by non-linear static analysis of the nominally perfect panels

Perfect geometry

With imperfection 2

With imperfection 1

Fig 23 Initial buckling mode shapes predicted by the non-linear analyses of Panel A1

Fig 22 Load-displacement, Panel A1

shapes predicted by the nonlinear analysis of panels A3 and A5 are also similar ie two inward buckles across the panel width as shown on Fig 21. Although similar, the predicted post-buckled mode shapes do not exactly agree with those adopted immediately after buckling on test.

STAGSC-1 Analysis of Panel A1 with Assumed Imperfection

Nonlinear analyses were carried out to compare the effect of small assumed imperfections on the response of panel A1. The results given on Fig 22 show the experimental behaviour compared with three theoretical load-displacement curves defined as follows:

- (a) The perfect panel response.
- (b) The response with an imperfection in the form of the experimental post-buckled mode shape just before failure, ie three buckles along and across the panel with amplitude 5% of thickness - defined as imperfection 1.
- (c) The response with an imperfection of the same size and shape as in (b) but directed in the opposite sense - defined as imperfection 2.

It was necessary both in the case of the perfect panel and with imperfection 2 to use a quarter model with the same mesh size in order to achieve results in the post-buckled region. Appropriate boundary conditions were used along the lines of symmetry.

It is apparent from Fig 22 that the predicted buckling load is reduced only slightly by imperfections, actually by 2.5% for imperfection 1 and by 3.5% for imperfection 2. The predicted initial buckling mode shapes all differ as shown on Fig 23. In the case of the perfect panel and that with imperfection 2 the difference is slight ie three buckles along the panel length as opposed to five. For imperfection 1 the initial buckling mode shape predicted is three inward buckles near each straight edge.

The development of the post buckled mode for the perfect panel is shown on Fig 24 showing a single central buckle followed by a mode consisting of three inward buckles running across both panel diagonals. The modal development for panel A1 with initial imperfections matching the test post buckled mode is shown on Fig 25. Excellent correspondence with the test behaviour is seen; two inward buckles symmetrically disposed about the centre line generator are followed by a further two at the top and bottom of the panel exactly as observed (see Fig 5). The nonlinear analysis of panel A1 has shown that small imperfections have little effect on the buckling load. Their influence appears to be limited to modifications of the predicted initial and post-buckled mode shapes.

Analysis of Geometrically Imperfect Panels

Panels A7-A9 were analysed using the STAGSC-1 code with imperfections modelled as half sine waves of the appropriate amplitude. The results are summarised in Table 2. The bifurcation analysis predicted a range of initial buckling loads from 171 kN for panel A8 (0.5 mm inward imperfections) to 176 kN for panel A9 (0.9 mm outward imperfection). We note that the corresponding result for the perfect panel A3 lies between those for panels with inward and outward imperfections respectively. The theory therefore agrees with established thinking that outward imperfections can

1st mode for perfect geometry (similar for panel with imperfection 2)

1st mode

Maximum deflection 7.43 mm
Load = 76.4 kN, displacement = 0.79 mm

2nd mode for perfect geometry

*Maximum out-of-plane displacement = 22.163 mm
Load = 72.412 kN, end shortening = 2.76938 mm
($\frac{1}{4}$ model with symmetry boundary conditions on edges internal to panel)

2nd mode

Maximum deflection 17.4 mm
Load = 77.6 kN, displacement = 2.16 mm

Fig 24 Post-buckled mode shapes predicted by the non-linear analysis of Panel A1

Fig 25 Post-buckled mode shapes predicted by the non-linear static analyses of Panel A1 with imperfection 1

Panel A1
(similar for panels A2 and A6)

Panel A5
(similar for Panel A4)

Panel A3
(similar for Panels A7, A8 and A9)

Fig 26 Initial buckling mode shapes predicted by the bifurcation analyses

slightly increase buckling loads while inward imperfections reduce them. However, the same trends were not observed from the test results. The buckling loads given in Table II for these analyses follow the same trend as those given by the bifurcation analyses, but the loads are generally 6% lower.

Effect of Non-uniform Loading on the STAGSC-1 Bifurcation Analysis Predictions

The possibility of slightly non-uniform loading always exists in compression testing of panels and this may lead to reduced buckling loads being obtained. This possibility was studied using the bifurcation analysis with linear end displacements giving a 10% load variation from one side of the panel to the other. The results for buckling load are given in Table III compared with those for uniform loading. At buckling the load across the panels still varies by 10% but the total load is only 2% less than that for uniform loading in the majority of cases. Somewhat greater reductions of 3.5% are found for panels A3, and A7-A9. For each panel tested the initial buckling mode shape predicted by both the non-uniform and the uniform loading analyses are very similar, the only difference being the greater depth of the buckles at the areas experiencing the greater loading. This can be seen by comparing Figs 19 and 26 which show the three different initial buckling mode shapes.

Analysis using BUCCAL and VIPASA

The Rayleigh-Ritz program BUCCAL⁶ was used to give linear eigenvalue predictions of initial buckling load and mode. In this program the curved panel is not divided into discrete elements but the deflections over the entire surface are approximated by a double Fourier series containing enough terms to adequately represent the initial buckling mode which is calculated within the analysis. Seven terms were used in both the deflection and force trial functions and the boundary conditions were set to match the test conditions.

VIPASA⁷ is a finite strip based program intended for the initial buckling and vibration analysis of long prismatic flat plate assemblies. Approximate analysis of curved panels is also possible by modelling the cross section as a series of flat strip elements. The element stiffness matrix is derived from a deflection field varying sinusoidally in the longitudinal direction with polynomial variation across the strip. Buckling loads are calculated for individual values of λ , the longitudinal modal half-wavelength, and the minimum load with corresponding mode is then selected. The present panels were modelled as 20 strips with subtended angle at the centre of curvature of 5° . Simply supported longitudinal edge conditions were applied as in the tests but the true support conditions at the loaded ends cannot be represented.

The results for initial buckling load of BUCCAL and VIPASA are given in Table II for comparison with the STAGSC-1 results and the experimental results. In the case of VIPASA the agreement ranges from -2.8% for panel A3 to +16.3% for panel A6. No consistent over-estimation was found as expected. These results for buckling load are good for panels of this type but it was noticed that the use of large numbers of strips gives excessively low predictions and the results do not converge. The modelling with a 5° subtended angle strip used in this work proved to be a satisfactory compromise. Similar to the FE method BUCCAL consistently over-predicted the measured values by differences ranging between 7.5% and 26%. However, apart from the expected general trend, no correlation was found between the results of STAGSC-1 and BUCCAL for the individual panels analysed.

We note in the comparison of methods that BUCCAL and VIPASA give extremely quick results, a few seconds only, compared with STAGSC-1 which can take several hours of processor time to carry out a nonlinear analysis.

Discussion and Conclusions

The behaviour of deeply curved CFRP compression panels tested under controlled displacement is summarised below:-

- (a) Pre-buckling behaviour is linear with small outward barrelling deflection superimposed with several small waves increasing in intensity up to the buckling point.
- (b) Violent snap buckling occurs resulting in up to 50% load loss with no apparent damage. The panels could be buckled several times at repeatable loads.
- (c) Post-buckled modes vary in form according to lay-up and magnitude of imperfection although the buckling load shows little sensitivity with mode.
- (d) Ultimate panel failure takes place at a lower load than initial buckling at end shortening values equivalent to a membrane strain of about 6000 $\mu\epsilon$ with considerably greater strain of about 8000 $\mu\epsilon$ at buckle peaks.
- (e) The effect of geometric imperfections at least for magnitudes up to $\frac{1}{2}$ panel thickness have very little influence on buckling load.

It is apparent from the above that the main requirement for CFRP panels of high curvature is to predict the initial buckling load, since in most practical loading situations buckling will cause failure. Considering first the finite element predictions for the nominally perfect panels using the STAGSC-1 code the bifurcation buckling analysis results were higher than experiment with differences ranging between +6.7% in the best case (panel A4) to +29% in the worst case (panel A3). The use of nonlinear static analysis to find the limit point did not always give a lower prediction; only in the case of panel A3 was a significant improvement made which brought agreement to within 21% of test. Given the high panel curvature resulting in violent snap buckling characteristics with large deflections and rotations the FE predictions using flat elements not specifically designed for curved surface analysis are considered to be quite good. Furthermore the general trends of pre and post-buckling behaviour observed **experimentally** are matched well by the analysis using the STAGSC-1 code. Turning to the finite strip and Rayleigh-Ritz based programs it was found that similar accuracy could be obtained, varying between - 2.8% to +16.3% in the case of VIPASA and from +7.5% to +26.2% in the case of BUCCAL. We note that, like the FE program STAGSC-1, BUCCAL always over-estimated the test results as expected whereas VIPASA gave lower results in some cases.

The study of the effect of imperfections as a potential cause of reduction in buckling load has shown that lateral bulges of up to half panel thickness make no more than a few percent difference to either the measured or predicted buckling loads. Furthermore no correlation was found between imperfection direction and load. In some of the tests two different forms of post buckled mode occurred at the same buckling load on successive tests of the same panel both of which differed from the initial buckling mode of relatively short wavelength waves. It can therefore be concluded that sensitivity of buckling load to initial or post-buckled mode is small and small imperfections of any shape or direction are unlikely to influence the buckling load for panels of this type.

The effect of load-non-uniformity in the tests as a potential experimental load reduction was studied using the STAGSC-1 code. A variation across the panel of 10% in load gave a reduction in total buckling load of less than 2%. This source of reduction cannot therefore explain the theoretical/experimental differences. Another factor which could cause overpredictions for the buckling loads of composite structures is the use of high orthotropic stiffness values, particularly the value for longitudinal Young's modulus, E_{11} . However, checks against the panel strain gauge results together with existing data for the XAS-914C material confirm the value used. Similarly flexural stiffness, proportional to the square of the thickness, depends critically on accurate thickness measurement. The thickness of 2 mm used here was derived from extensive measurement at many points over the panels so this factor can also be excluded.

The present differences between theory and test results cannot be explained straightforwardly, although the high curvature and violent snap buckling behaviour with large rotations both lead to great difficulties in analysis. Indeed the results from all the methods used are considered most encouraging. The use of a flat element is less than ideal in these cases and the development of reliable shell elements capable of large rotations should improve accuracy. Considering the implications for design it appears that the finite strip and Rayleigh-Ritz methods give similar accuracy to the finite element methods for the analysis of discrete panels, but they have the advantages of greater speed and simpler data input requirements. The prediction of safe loading levels must take into account the load loss at buckling and, as in metal design practice of highly curved panels, the maximum load must be set well below the buckling load. Further work is underway at RAE to test and analyse panels with less curvature (500 mm and 1000 mm radius) and general recommendations for design must await the assessment of these and other results.

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